

Pythagoras via Ptolemy

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The Pythagorean Theorem is immediate for an isosceles right triangle:

Thus, completing the square, the area of the blue triangle is obviously

$$b^2/2$$

but also

$$c^2/4$$

hence

$$c^2 = b^2 + b^2$$

More generally, using this idea on a right triangle with unequal sides

leads to an inscribed isosceles trapezoid whose (dashed) diagonal is the length of interest:

Now, it is algebraically evident that

$$(a - b)^2 + (\sqrt{2}a)(\sqrt{2}b) = a^2 + b^2$$

and by Ptolemy's Theorem the left-hand side here is exactly the trapezoid diagonal squared.